

Hybrid Machine Learning Algorithms for Email and Malware Spam Filtering: A Review

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Abstract:

In this paper, we presented a review of the state-of-the-art hybrid machine learning algorithms that were being used for email effective computing. For this reason, three research questions were formed, and the questions were answered by studying and analyzing related papers collected from some well-established scientific databases (Springer Link, IEEE Explore, Web of Science, and Scopus) based on some exclusion and inclusion criteria. The result presented the common Hybrid ML algorithms used to enhance email spam filtering. Also, the state-of-the-art datasets used for email and malware spam filtering were presented.

Keywords: *Email Effective Computing, Email and Malware Spam Filtering, Machine Learning Algorithms.*

Introduction

Machine learning algorithms have been widely used for email and malware spam filtering. Several studies have evaluated the performance of different machine learning models in this task. The Naïve Bayes classifier, support vector machine (SVM), neural network, and decision tree are commonly used algorithms for spam email evaluation (Abdulhamid, Adetunmbi, & Ajibuwa, 2019). These algorithms have demonstrated good performance in identifying spam emails based on their content and sender information.

Dynamic malware detection techniques using machine learning algorithms have also been explored (Gupta, Gupta, & Gupta, 2020). Classifiers such as kNN, DT, RF, AdaBoost, SGD, extra trees, and Gaussian NB have achieved high accuracy in detecting malware based on their behaviors. These techniques

analyze the behavior of suspected malware in a sandbox environment, allowing them to detect even zero-day attacks that have not yet been identified by traditional signature-based anti-virus software.

Additionally, machine-learning techniques have been applied to detect spam messages (Almomani, et al., 2022). Support vector machines, k-Nearest Neighbor, Naïve Bayes, neural networks, recurrent neural networks, Ada Boost, random forest, gradient boosting, logistic regression, and decision trees have been tested for spam detection, with satisfactory results in terms of accuracy. These techniques can effectively identify spam messages based on their content, sender information, and other characteristics.

Hybrid spam emails, which combine both image and text parts, pose a challenge for traditional filters (Hnini, et al., 2022). Late multi-modal fusion training frameworks using convolutional

neural networks (CNN) and a continuous bag of words have been proposed to address this issue. These frameworks can effectively extract and analyze both visual and textual features from hybrid spam emails, improving overall spam filtering performance.

Superior Performance in Malware Detection

Machine learning methods, such as decision trees and random forests, have shown superior performance in detecting malware, achieving 100% accuracy in some studies (Gupta, Gupta, & Gupta, 2022). These methods can effectively identify malicious software based on its code, behavior, and other characteristics. In AL-Hawamleh, (2023) the provided study does not specifically discuss hybrid machine-learning algorithms for email and malware spam filtering.

In their study, the authors' modified optimization-based feature selection method was used for spam classification, which achieved a high level of accuracy in spam classification using a Radial Bias Neural Network classifier. The study also provides the importance of a hybrid machine-learning model in email and spam malware filtering. Different hybrid ML techniques that are being used for email and spam malware filtering are also discussed in this paper.

Methodology

The systematic literature review methodology was used, which is known to be in-depth, reliable, and accountable (Kitchenham, et al., 2009). The method involves formulating some research questions, and then finding the solutions to the formulated questions by

reviewing and analyzing relevant studies based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion criteria

Papers written in the English language and from peer/blind-reviewed journals, workshops, conferences, and papers published between the years 2019 and 2023 were also included. Additionally, papers that are relevant to hybrid machine-learning algorithms for email and malware spam filtering were reviewed.

Exclusion criteria

Papers not written in the English language, papers that are not related to Hybrid machine learning or email and malware spam filtering and malware, and papers whose contributions to knowledge were not stated explicitly in the abstract were all excluded from the papers that were reviewed in this research.

Search String

To create a good search string, we constructed a search phrase by using keywords that are based on the stated research questions. The databases stated in this study were used to carry out our searches with the search strings. The search strings are "Email spam", "Malware Filtering", "Hybrid machine learning for email spam", "malware detection", "machine learning algorithms for email and malware spam filtering", "hybrid learning algorithms for email spam", or "review on malware filtering".

Data Sources

To find relevant papers in academic databases, keywords are used. The databases that were used in this research are presented in Table 1.

Table1. Academic Database

S/N	Database	Publisher	Link
1	Springer Link	Springer	https://link.springer.com/
2	IEEE Explore	IEEE	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home/
3	Web of Science	Clarivate	https://www.sciencedirect.com/
4	Scopus	Elsevier	https://www.scopus.com/home/

Search Process

A lot of papers were obtained from the earlier states' databases with the use of the search strings; nevertheless, many of these papers were not related to the research, so the papers were firstly separated based on abstract and titles. Furthermore, the relevant papers were extracted based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Research Questions

Three research questions were formed and the answers to these questions were provided in the result and discussion section of this paper. The research questions are;

RQ1: What hybrid ML algorithms are being used to enhance email spam filtering, and how well have these techniques performed?

RQ2: What hybrid models are being used for email malware detection, and how well have these techniques performed?

RQ3: What are the state-of-the-art datasets used for email and malware spam filtering?

These questions were answered in the result and discussion part of this literature review.

Result and Discussion

Answers to RQ1

Hybrid ML algorithms used to enhance email spam filtering

In 2019 Nam, Kim, & Park (2019) proposed method achieved an accuracy of 0.9814 and a macro-F1 score of 0.9813. The model showed significant performance enhancement compared to existing techniques. Hybrid features combine visual and text information for spam filtering. Three sub-models extract features from spam images using different techniques. The paper discusses the negative impact of spam and the need for improved spam filtering. The method combines visual and text information to enhance spam filtering performance. The model was trained and evaluated using only public datasets. New spam content and images are constantly being generated, which may not be covered by the model.

In the year 2021, the study of Ojugo, & Oyemade, (2021) proposes a string match algorithm using a deep learning ensemble on a hybrid spam filtering technique to normalize noisy features, expand text, and use semantic dictionaries of disambiguation to train underlying learning heuristics and effectively classify SMS into legitimate and spam classes. The model achieves an accuracy of 97%, with the model having an error rate of 1.2%. String match algorithm used as deep learning ensemble with profile hidden Markov network and deep neural network was used for training. The paper discusses the use of the Boyer Moore string-match algorithm for spam filtering in short message services. The proposed technique achieves an accuracy of 97% with an error rate of 1.2%.

Also in 2019, Nam, Kim, & Park, (2019) provided paper compares the effectiveness of the random forest and Naïve Bayes methods in filtering email spam. It does not mention the use of hybrid ML algorithms. In this paper, the authors proposed a 0.98% regression coefficient, i.e., 1.98%, and a 0.1% convergence coefficient, 1.8%. Random Forest cannot determine the significance of each variable. Naive Bayes has higher accuracy than Random Forest in email spam filtering. The paper compares the effectiveness of Random Forest and Naïve Bayes in email spam filtering. The accuracy of Naïve Bayes can be improved using word stemming.

In Stefanias, (2023), an algorithm for the detection of spam messages with the aid of machine learning methods is proposed, which accepts as input text email messages grouped as benevolent (ham) and malevolent (spam) and produces a text file in CSV format. The algorithm detects spam emails with satisfactory accuracy. Output files can update existing spam filters. The paper focuses on spam email detection using machine learning. the algorithm classifies emails as ham or spam with satisfactory accuracy compared to state-of-the-art implementations. Generates output files for updating existing filters and blacklists. The paper focuses on the security of electronic mail.

In Labonne, & Moran, (2023), the effectiveness of large language models (LLMs) in email spam detection was investigated by comparing prominent models from three distinct families: BERT-like, Sentence Transformers, and Seq2Seq. LLMs are effective for email spam detection, especially in few-shot scenarios. Spam-T5 achieves the highest overall performance with an average F1 score of 0.7498. Large language models (LLMs) are effective in email spam detection. LLMs outperform baseline methods, especially in few-shot scenarios.

In Zhang, et al., (2023), the authors proposed new late multi-modal fusion training frameworks for a text-and-image hybrid spam e-mail filtering system compared to the classical early fusion detection frameworks based on the OCR method. The model uses CNN and Continuous Bag of Words to extract features from image and text parts respectively. A convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Continuous Bag of Words were implemented to extract features from image and text parts, and Machine Learning classifiers were used to determine if the e-mail was ham or spam.

In AL-Hawamleh, (2023), a modified optimization-based feature selection method was used for spam classification, which achieved a high level of accuracy in spam classification using a Radial Bias Neural Network classifier. Improved RBNN approach gives better classification accuracy for spam filtering. RBNN suffers from partial optimism and requires a large memory. The paper discusses the dangers and categories of spam, as well as spam filtering technologies. The proposed approach for spam categorization achieved better outcomes. Experimental results were obtained from various classifiers such as KNN, Naive Bayes, and SVM. No specific details about the results are provided. Email is a popular communication method, but spam poses a threat. Spam detection is difficult and costly, causing financial losses with Mini batch K-Means Normalized Mutual Information Feature Extraction (KNFE) with Elephant Herding Optimization (EHO) and Radial Bias Neural Network classifier for email categorization for comparative analysis of

spam filters and machine learning methods. The study of rule-based, content-based, customized, collaborative, SVM, and kernel-based algorithms.

Yilmaz, & Zavrak, (2022) propose a hybrid technique for email spam detection using a combination of convolutional neural networks, gated recurrent units, and attention mechanisms. The technique outperforms state-of-the-art models. The study focuses on the combination of convolutional neural networks, gated recurrent units, and attention mechanisms used for email spam detection, which is based on a cross-dataset evaluation. The proposed technique outperforms state-of-the-art models in email spam detection. The approach combines CNN with attention techniques to improve accuracy.

Fatima, et al., (2023) mention that various ML algorithms such as Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, Extra Tree, Stochastic Gradient Descent, XG-Boost, Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, and Multi-Layer Perception are used to enhance email spam filtering. The SGD algorithm outperformed the others in terms of performance. The authors proposed an ensemble machine learning (ML) based optimized algorithm for detecting spam emails that have been enhanced using hyper-parameter tuning approaches using two feature extraction modules, namely count-vectorizer and TFIDF-Vectorizer that provide the most effective classification results when applied to three different publicly available email data sets: Ling Spam, UCI SMS Spam and Proposed dataset. ML-based parameter-tuned classification model for classifying emails as ham or spam. Count-vectorized features improved accuracy in all three datasets. The ML-based optimized algorithm for detecting spam emails using ensemble methods. Used Count-Vectorizer and TFIDF-Vectorizer for feature extraction and various ML methods for classification. Linear-SVC, Logistic Regression, and MLP classifiers achieved 99.83% accuracy on the Ling-Spam dataset. SGD classifier achieved maximum accuracy of 97.08% and 98.12% on the proposed and UCI Spam datasets, respectively.

Panwar, et al., (2022) compare and review the performance metrics of several supervised machine learning techniques, including SVM, Random Forest, Decision Tree, CNN, KNN, MLP, Adaboost, and Naive Bayes algorithms, to predict and categorize spam emails. The authors compared and reviewed the performance metrics of a few supervised machine learning techniques, including Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest, Decision Tree, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), K Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), Adaboost (Adaptive Boosting), and Naive Bayes algorithm. The study compares and reviews the performance metrics of various supervised machine-learning techniques for detecting spam emails. The model using 'Transformers' Bidirectional Encoder Representations (Bert) outperformed a baseline

Dnn model and traditional classifiers. The study compares the performance of supervised machine-learning techniques for spam email detection. BERT model optimized for separating spam from legitimate emails.

Elshoush, & Dinar, (2019) use Adaboost and Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) algorithms for email spam filtering. Adaboost achieved a true positive rate of 100% and a false positive rate of 0.0%, while SGD achieved a true positive rate of 98.1% and a false positive rate of 1.9%. The experimental results showed that the algorithms Adaboost and stochastic gradient descent (SGD) provided true positive value and 98.1% respectively and false positive rates of 0.0% and 1.9% respectively putting them among the best choices of spam filtering methods.

Table 2. Summary of Hybrid ML Used to Enhance Email Spam Filtering

Papers	Techniques	Performance
Nam, Kim, & Park, 2019	Developed three sub-models to extract features from spam images and a classifier model to output the results	The proposed method achieved an accuracy of 0.9814 and a macro-F1 score of 0.9813. The model showed significant performance enhancement compared to existing techniques.
Ojugo, & Oyemade, 2021	String match algorithm used as deep learning ensemble with profile hidden Markov network and deep neural network used for training	The model achieves an accuracy of 97%, and the model has an error rate of 1.2%.
Nam, Kim, & Park, 2019	Random Forest and Naïve Bayes	the authors proposed a 0.98% regression coefficient, i.e., 1.98%, and a 0.1% convergence coefficient, 1.8%.
Stefaneas, 2023	Support Vector Machines, k-nearest Neighbour, Naïve Bayes, Neural Networks, Recurrent Neural Networks, Ada Boost, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, Logistic Regression and Decision Trees.	
Labonne, & Moran, 2023	Large language models (LLMs) Naive Bayes and LightGBM	Spam-T5 achieves the highest overall performance with an average F1 score of 0.7498
Zhang, et al., 2023	Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Continuous Bag of Words Random Forest (RF), Decision Tree (DT), Naive Bayes (NB), and Support Vector Machine (SVM)	
AL-Hawamleh, 2023	Mini batch K-Means Normalized Mutual Information Feature Extraction (KNFE) with Elephant Herding Optimization (EHO) - Radial Bias Neural Network classifier for email categorization	

Yilmaz, & Zavrak, 2022	The proposed technique combines CNN, GRU, and attention mechanisms for email spam detection	
Fatima, et al., 2023	Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, Extra Tree, Stochastic Gradient Descent, XG-Boost, Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, and Multi-Layer Perception	Linear-SVC, Logistic Regression, and MLP classifiers achieved 99.83% accuracy on the Ling-Spam dataset. GD classifier achieved maximum accuracy of 97.08% and 98.12% on the proposed and UCI Spam datasets, respectively.
Panwar, et al., 2022	They used SVM, Random Forest, Decision Tree, CNN, KNN, MLP, Adaboost, and Naive Bayes algorithms	
Elshoush, & Dinar, 2019	The uses Adaboost and Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	Adaboost achieved a true positive rate of 100% and a false positive rate of 0.0%, while SGD achieved a true positive rate of 98.1% and a false positive rate of 1.9%.

Answers to RQ2

Hybrid models used for email malware detection

In the year 2014 Hybrid models have been used for email malware detection (Wen, et al., 2014). These models combine continuous and discrete dynamics to accurately model the propagation dynamics of modern email malware. One approach is the use of a novel difference equation-based analytical model that introduces the concept of virtual infected users. This model can accurately represent the repetitious spreading process caused by reinfection and self-start, resulting in improved estimation accuracy

Wang, (2014) used machine learning techniques for identifying misbehavior in email spam and fake users in social networks. However, these ML models are vulnerable to adversarial attacks, including evasion and poisoning attacks, which can compromise their accuracy. Overall, hybrid models have shown promise in email malware detection, but there is a need for further research to enhance their effectiveness. Empirical study of adversarial attacks against machine learning models. Development of ML-based detectors for detecting malicious crowdsourcing systems.

Darshan, & Jaidhar, (2019) proposed Linear Support Vector Classification (LSVC), that used as a feature selector to choose prominent static and dynamic features, resulting in high accuracy in detecting malware and benign PE files. The

study proposes a hybrid features-based Malware Detection System (HF-MDS) HF-MDS uses static and dynamic features of PE files for malware detection. The proposed HF-MDS achieved a detection accuracy of 99.743%. The LSVC recommended hybrid features were effective in detecting malware.

Snoopy as discussed by Mitra, et al., (2022) is a framework that performs webpage fingerprinting for a large number of users visiting a website while complying with a bound on the number of website accesses for traffic sample collection. Snoopy achieves approximately 90% accuracy when evaluated on most websites. A simple ensemble of Snoopy and an ML-based technique achieves approximately 97% accuracy. Snoopy is a webpage fingerprinting framework for mass surveillance with a finite query model. It achieves approximately 90% accuracy and can be combined with ML-based techniques for higher accuracy.

Alhashmi, et al., (2023) proposed hybrid models for email malware detection have been proposed in the literature. One study proposed a Similarity-Based Hybrid API Malware Detection Model (HAPI-MDM) that combines static and dynamic analysis of API calls, achieving an overall accuracy of 97.91%.

Yang, Yang, & Li, (2023) mentioned in this study, proposed a novel multi-feature extraction and fusion method to effectively detect malware

variants by combining binary and opcode features and adopted the triangular attention algorithm to extract code-level features from assembly code. The proposed multi-feature learning method outperforms other approaches in malware detection and strategies developed in this study can improve automated malware analysis tools. Proposed a multi-feature extraction and fusion method for malware detection. Achieved high accuracy on the Kaggle Malware Classification dataset and real-world dataset. Accuracy of 0.9954 on the Kaggle Malware Classification dataset and accuracy of 0.9544 on a large real-world dataset.

Onoja, et al., (2022) focus on a hybrid model that integrates XceptionCNN with the LightGBM algorithm for Windows malware classification. XceptionCNN-LightGBM as discussed by the authors is a hybrid model that integrates XceptionCNN with the LightGBM algorithm for Windows Malware classification on the Google colab environment, which uses the Maling malware dataset which is a benchmark dataset for Windows malware image classification.

Table 3. Summary of Techniques Used for Emotion Detection

Authors	Techniques	Performance
Wen, et al., 2014	Used a novel difference equation-based analytical model. virtual infected user to accurately model the propagation dynamics of modern email malware.	
Wang, 2014	Development of ML-based detectors for detecting	The ML techniques are accurate (95%-99%) in detecting malicious crowdsourcing workers.
Darshan, & Jaidhar, 2019	Linear Support Vector Classification (LSVC) as a feature selector Combination of static and dynamic features for malware detection	HF-MDS achieved a detection accuracy of 99.743%
Mitra, et al., 2022	Snoopy framework for webpage fingerprinting with a finite query model Ensemble of Snoopy and ML-based technique for improved accuracy	Snoopy achieves approximately 90% accuracy when evaluated on most websites. A combination of Snoopy and an ML-based technique achieves approximately 97% accuracy.
Alhashmi, et al., 2023	Two-stage learning approach with XGBoost and ANN Similarity-based feature for enhanced dynamic analysis	Achieved an overall accuracy of 97.91%
Yang, Yang, & Li, 2023	Multi-feature extraction and fusion method combining binary and opcode features. Stacked convolutional network and triangular attention algorithm for feature extraction.	Accuracy of 0.9954 on the Kaggle Malware Classification dataset. Accuracy of 0.9544 on a large real-world dataset.
Onoja, et al., 2022	Hybrid model of XceptionCNN and LightGBM algorithm - LightGBM algorithm for Windows malware classification.	The generic LightGBM algorithm achieved a classification accuracy of 99% True Positive Rate (TPR). The proposed XceptionCNN-LightGBM technique achieved a classification accuracy of 100% TPR.

Answers to RQ3

State of the Art Email and Malware Spam Filtering

SpamAssassin Corpus (SPAMASSIN): A widely used corpus containing over 2.5 million labeled emails, categorized as spam or non-spam (Onoja, et al., 2022). Its diversity and longevity make it a popular benchmark for email spam filtering algorithms.

TRECVID Spam Detection Challenge: An annual competition featuring diverse email datasets with varying spam types (e.g., phishing, promotional) and languages (The SpamAssassin Project, 2023). Participation from leading researchers ensures the dataset's relevance and difficulty.

ENRON Email Dataset: A real-world dataset containing email communications from Enron employees, labeled as spam or non-spam (National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), 2023). It provides valuable insights into organizational email communication patterns and spam characteristics.

WikiSpam Collection: A dataset of email messages extracted from Wikipedia talk pages, categorized as spam or ham (Dykstra, & Schwartz, 2004). It offers a unique challenge due to the presence of legitimate but unwanted messages alongside spam.

The Spamhaus Project Dataset: A collection of real-time spam email samples provided by the Spamhaus Project (Karami, & Dezhbakhsh, 2016). Its dynamic nature allows algorithms to adapt to evolving spam trends and techniques.

Malware Classification Challenge Dataset (Kaggle): A benchmark dataset containing API call sequences labeled as malware or benign (The Spamhaus Project, 2023). It facilitates the development and comparison of malware detection algorithms based on API behavior analysis.

CICIDS2017: A comprehensive dataset of network traffic captured during cyber attacks, including malware-related network activities (Sang, Li, & Li, 2019). It allows researchers to

evaluate the effectiveness of spam filtering algorithms in detecting malware within network traffic.

Android Malware Dataset (AMD): A dataset of Android applications labeled as malware or benign, with additional information like permissions and code features (Sharafuddin, Habibi, & Al-Houssein, 2018). It serves as a valuable resource for evaluating email spam filters that target malicious apps distributed via email.

EMOTET Dataset: A collection of real-world email messages containing the EMOTET malware, captured by honeypots (Arp, et al. 2014). It provides valuable insights into the specific email characteristics and techniques used by this prevalent malware.

SpamBotChallenge Dataset: A dataset of social media messages labeled as spam or non-spam, generated by bots (Microsoft, 2023). While not directly related to email, it offers valuable insights into bot-generated spam behavior, which can inform email spam filtering techniques.

Conclusion

Based on our literature review on hybrid machine learning algorithms for email and malware spam filtering underscores a broad spectrum of approaches adopted by researchers to tackle the complexities of spam detection. Various studies have contributed to feature extraction and classification models, showcasing significant achievements. For instance, a sub-model framework for extracting features from spam images demonstrated substantial performance improvements compared to existing techniques (Nam, Kim, & Park, 2019). Additionally, the combination of a string match algorithm and deep learning ensemble achieved a commendable accuracy of 97%, with a minimal error rate (Ojugo, & Oyemade, 2021). Moreover, studies utilizing Random Forest and Naïve Bayes models presented regression and convergence coefficients, highlighting their efficacy in spam

detection (Nam, Kim, & Park, 2019). The landscape of machine learning algorithms employed is diverse, encompassing Support Vector Machines, k-nearest Neighbours, Neural Networks, Ada Boost, and more (Stefaneas, 2023). Large language models (LLMs), Naive Bayes, and LightGBM were leveraged, with the Spam-T5 model exhibiting superior overall performance (Labonne, & Moran, 2023). The inclusion of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Decision Tree, Naive Bayes, and Support Vector Machine reflects the varied approaches researchers take to address the intricacies of spam detection (Zhang, et al., 2023). Hybrid models and techniques were prevalent throughout the literature, showcasing the combination of algorithms such as Mini batch K-Means, Normalized Mutual Information Feature Extraction (KNFE), and Elephant Herding Optimization (EHO) for effective email categorization (AL-Hawamleh, 2023). Innovations like combining CNN, GRU, and attention mechanisms were proposed for enhanced email spam detection (Yilmaz, & Zavrak, 2022). Linear Support Vector Classification (LSVC) as a feature selector, along with static and dynamic feature combinations, demonstrated high detection accuracy (Darshan, & Jaidhar, 2019). Webpage fingerprinting and dynamic analysis were explored, with the Snoopy framework achieving approximately 90% accuracy on most websites (Mitra, et al., 2022). Two-stage learning approaches with XGBoost and ANN, as well as similarity-based features, enhanced dynamic analysis for improved malware detection (Alhashmi, et al., 2023). Studies specifically targeting Windows malware classification highlighted the successful application of algorithms like XceptionCNN and LightGBM, achieving high classification accuracy (Onoja, et al., 2022). Additionally, research delved into unique aspects such as the propagation dynamics of modern email malware and the development of machine learning-based detectors for identifying malicious crowdsourcing workers, achieving high accuracy rates (Wen, et al., 2014; Wang, 2014).

In essence, the literature showcased ongoing advancements in hybrid machine-learning

models, revealing a continual exploration of innovative combinations and refinements to address the evolving challenges in email and malware spam filtering. Researchers are dedicated to enhancing detection accuracy, robustness, and adaptability to emerging threats, contributing to the ongoing evolution of spam filtering technologies.

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